

Comparative Stress Testing of Kubernetes Distributions and CNI Plugins

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Abstract—Kubernetes (K8s) facilitates automated deployment and scaling within containerized environments, providing various distributions and network alternatives to accommodate diverse application requirements. In this regard, selecting the appropriate K8s configuration can lead to improved network communication, better resource utilization, and enhanced overall system efficiency. In this paper, we present a comprehensive evaluation of four K8s implementations, along with two well-known Container Network Interface (CNI) plugins, under diverse and realistic stress-intensive workloads. Our experimentation methodology involves utilizing different stress-testing tools and deployment workloads, i.e., custom pod deployment scripts and the Kube-burner tool, providing valuable insights into the resource footprint and performance (e.g., effectiveness, pod latency and readiness) of the evaluated K8s and CNIs.

Index Terms—Edge-Cloud Computing, Kubernetes, Distributions, CNI plugins, Stress-Testing

I. INTRODUCTION

Edge-cloud infrastructures support a wide range of services and use-cases, from smart-city deployments to industrial IoT and remote health, each with a diverse set of application requirements. For instance, large-scale production deployments (e.g., enterprise applications) prioritize reliability, scalability and fault tolerance, while edge-oriented workloads (e.g., on Raspberry Pi or edge gateways) focus on maintaining minimal resource overhead, energy efficiency, and rapid deployment.

Kubernetes (K8s) has emerged as the de facto container orchestration system to manage edge-cloud deployments, providing various distributions and plugins, tailored to different deployment scenarios and workloads. In this context, lightweight K8s such as K3s, K0s, and MicroK8s have emerged as typical solutions to support resource-constrained environments [1], in contrast to the standard vanilla K8s. In a similar vein, networking plugins such as Flannel and Weavenet are known to provide a lower resource footprint compared to other feature-rich solutions such as Kube-OVN and Cilium [2]. However, several recent studies [3], [4], including our findings in [5], demonstrate that the selection of a lightweight K8s distribution or CNI plugin does not ensure lower resource usage or higher network efficiency, since the latter also depends on the requirements of the deployment scenario.

In this research front, stress testing may offer crucial insights regarding the performance of the different K8s distributions and networking configurations, e.g., in terms of scalability lim-

itations or bottlenecks identification. Existing studies primarily focus on stressing specific K8s distributions [6] or networking approaches [2], often based on specific metrics (e.g., CPU [7]) and benchmarks [8] which may not reflect the demands of realistic scenarios, also ignoring the impact of underlying networking fabrics on the overall performance [9]. Therefore, there is a strong need for thorough experimentation to address these aspects simultaneously.

To bridge this research gap, we extend our prior work presented in [3] and [5] by evaluating the performance of different K8s distributions and CNI plugins in realistic stressing scenarios with varying stress intensities. The major contributions of this work are outlined below:

- Conduct a comprehensive evaluation of K8s distributions across various stressing tools and deployments, assessing cluster performance under real-world workloads while identifying key performance and resource consumption trade-offs.
- Consider the selection of CNI plugins as an additional factor when stressing K8s distributions, showcasing how networking fabrics affect cluster performance.
- Exploit performance evaluation metrics covering both cluster's lifecycle behavior, e.g., pod readiness times, and pod latency, as well as real-time resource utilization, e.g., CPU and RAM consumption, through the utilization of our novel experimentation framework, i.e., CODEF [10].

Along these lines, we assess 4 K8s distributions, including both lightweight implementations (K3s, K0s, MicroK8s) and standard K8s, along with 2 widely-used CNI plugins (Calico and Flannel). We conduct a set of stress-testing scenarios, analyzing the performance of the distributions and plugins. In particular, we focused on the pod startup times as the number of deployed pods scaled up, as well as on the pod latency under two distinct experimental conditions characterized by varying intensity levels, leveraging the Kube-burner tool to generate these workloads. Throughout these experiments, we also gather resource utilization metrics, specifically CPU and memory usage. Our results offer valuable insights into the performance characteristics, operational efficiency, and trade-offs associated with these K8s components.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we discuss related works that consider K8s config-

urations’ stressing. In Section III we outline the characteristics of the evaluated distributions and CNI plugins. In Section IV we describe our experimentation setup and methodology, while in Section V we present results of the experiments. Finally, Sections VI and VII detail the insights gained by our analysis along with our concluding remarks and future plans.

II. RELATED WORK

Several recent studies focus on the performance of different K8s cluster configurations under various stress and workload scenarios. For example, [1] provides a comparative analysis between lightweight K8s distributions through stress-inducing workloads, focusing on system resources and traditional cluster API calls. Similarly, in [11], authors evaluate 5 lightweight K8s distributions through stress testing distinct phases of the pod lifecycle, i.e., pod initiation, scheduling latency, and readiness time metrics, putting particular attention on scheduling performance. In addition, [9] focuses on the task of scheduling and pod-lifecycle management in a large-scale K8s cluster, highlighting the response times of K8s API endpoints through the use of Kubemark. The paper in [8] stresses different system resources (e.g., CPU, memory, disk, network) for 4 cloud-hosted environments. Moreover, [7] presents a performance assessment of multiple K8s distributions deployed on heterogeneous x86 and ARM CPU architectures, including scalability, cost, and overall performance.

Other relevant works focus on the impact of CNI plugins over different networking processes. For example, [2] offers a comprehensive comparison of diverse CNI plugins by evaluating their functionality (e.g., packet forwarding and routing), as well as their performance and scalability under varying HTTP workloads. On the other hand, some studies, e.g., [6], [4], and [12], explore the performance of lightweight K8s distributions during cluster lifecycle stages (i.e., startup, deployment and shutdown) and resource consumption (i.e., CPU, memory, and disk utilization) in edge computing scenarios.

To the best of our knowledge, our previous work in [5] is the first examining the interplay between lightweight K8s distributions and different networking plugins. However, that study did not incorporate applications or workloads that could increase the resource intensity and stress the system’s performance. The current work addresses this gap by introducing realistic stress-testing scenarios that increase system load and provide valuable insights into the trade-offs associated with different K8s distributions and networking fabrics.

III. KUBERNETES DISTRIBUTIONS & CNI PLUGINS

In this section, we outline key characteristics of the K8s distributions and CNI plugins considered in our analysis.

A. Kubernetes distributions

We examine four K8s implementations, namely vanilla K8s, K3s, K0s, and MicroK8s, with the latter three considered lightweight distributions designed for edge environments.

Vanilla K8s is a robust container orchestration platform, maintained as the standard distribution. It offers built-in high

availability, full API support and fine-grained role-based access control, making it especially suited for large-scale, production-grade deployments and requiring at least 2 CPUs and 2 GB of RAM.

K3s, maintained by SUSE, is optimized for resource-constrained scenarios, such as edge computing, IoT and embedded systems (1 CPU and 1 GB RAM). It reduces the K8s overhead by bundling its components into a single binary, using SQLite instead of etcd and integrating Containerd instead of requiring full Docker support.

K0s, maintained by Mirantis, is designed specifically for easy deployment across diverse and resource-constrained infrastructures. It emphasizes simplicity and minimal resource usage by bundling core components into a single binary (requiring less than 1 CPU and 1 GB RAM). Unlike traditional K8s, K0s separates the control plane from worker nodes and utilizes Konnectivity agents to securely proxy communication between the API server and the workers.

MicroK8s (referred here as MK8s) is maintained by Canonical, designed to provide an easy-to-install local K8s for both constrained environments and small-scale production (with recommended requirements of 2-core CPU and 4 GB RAM). It is packaged as a Snap for fast deployment, automatic updates and self-healing mechanisms while it includes easily-enabled add-ons such as Istio, Helm, Prometheus, and Grafana.

B. CNI plugins

Flannel is a lightweight CNI plugin designed for simple, Layer 3 overlay networking in K8s clusters. It deploys a flannel daemon on each node in the cluster and uses VXLAN, UDP, or host-gw to create a flat network. Flannel does not support advanced network policies, making it primarily used for basic K8s networking and small to medium-sized clusters but less suited for security-focused environments.

Calico is a Layer 3/4 CNI plugin providing advanced networking capabilities and security policies for K8s. It supports both BGP-based pure Layer 3 networking without overlays and VXLAN/IP-in-IP encapsulation. Calico enables fine-grained NetworkPolicies, allowing control over pod-to-pod, namespace, and security features, including services meshes (e.g., Istio), Wireguard and eXpress Data Path. It also provides Vector Packet Processor and extended Berkeley Packet Filter data planes, and kube-proxy modes such as iptables and IPVS.

IV. EXPERIMENTATION SETUP AND METHODOLOGY

This section provides an overview of our experimentation approach (see Fig. 1), including our setup description and details on the considered experimentation scenarios, i.e., (i) resource consumption in idle state; (ii) pod readiness times; and (iii) pod latency and resource utilization while running two distinct stress-testing scenarios using Kube-burner [13]; with an increasing number of pods/applications. In this evaluation, we consider four K8s distributions, i.e., vanilla K8s, K3s, K0s, and MK8s, each paired with either Calico or Flannel as CNI plugin. Note, that K0s-Flannel is excluded, as it is not supported by the official K0s documentation. To ensure

Fig. 1: Experimentation Methodology.

TABLE I: System Specifications.

Parameter	System Specifications
Cluster Nodes	3 (1 Control Plane & 2 Workers)
Hardware (per node)	4GB CPU(s) & RAM, 40GB storage
Kernel Version	5.15.0
Containerd Version	1.7.26
Kubernetes Distribution	K8s, K3s, K0s, MicroK8s
Kubernetes Version	1.31
CNI Plugin & Version	Calico (v3.29.1), Flannel (v0.26.4)

reliability, we conducted all experiments over 10 iterations, incorporating a cooldown period between each iteration for system cooling.

A. System Specs

The testbed environment is hosted on a Dell PowerEdge T640 server equipped with an Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4210R at 2.40GHz, 16 cores CPU, 64GB RAM and 1TB NVMe SSD, running the XCP-ng virtualization platform [14]. The server is configured with a 100Mbit/s NIC and a 10G X550T Ethernet controller for networking. The setup includes all cluster VMs i.e., 1 master and 2 worker nodes which are automatically deployed utilizing the CODECO Experimentation Framework (CODEF) [10] with full system specifications provided in Table I. Using the CODEF, we ensure consistent and reproducible evaluation across all experiments, as clusters are removed and then automatically redeployed from scratch in an identical manner.

B. Pod Readiness Time

The readiness time refers to the time required by pods to transition to "Ready" state. This metric is critical in the lifecycle of cluster as it directly influences its responsiveness and reliability, particularly in scenarios requiring rapid scaling. It is also valuable for assessing how various networking configurations (e.g., CNI plugins) impact application performance, as they manage networking in distinct ways, and thus affect how quickly pods obtain IP addresses, establish routes and become network-ready. In our experiments, we deploy pod batches (from 1 to 100) which are scheduled onto a designated worker node via a "nodeSelector" using a pre-installed "k8s.gcr.io/pause:3.1" container image to measure the average pod readiness time per batch.

TABLE II: Median (min, max) values of CPU (%) and RAM (MB) usage in idle state of master and worker nodes.

	Calico				Flannel		
	K8s	K3s	MK8s	K0s	K8s	K3s	MK8s
CPU master	2.45 (2.38,4.55)	2.27 (2.17,4.82)	2.59 (2.51,4.29)	1.99 (1.94,3.22)	1.79 (1.75,3.71)	1.18 (1.14,1.84)	1.71 (1.63,3.03)
CPU worker	1.68 (1.47,3.02)	1.89 (1.82,2.9)	0.84 (0.79,1.14)	1.41 (1.37,2.18)	1.14 (1.1,2.77)	1.53 (1.5,3.42)	0.96 (0.92,1.59)
RAM master	1746 (1745,1809)	1699 (1696,1746)	1570 (1550,1603)	1280 (1279,1320)	1245 (1234,1261)	1202 (1199,1255)	1155 (1153,1218)
RAM worker	1263 (1261,1292)	1585 (1583,1635)	762 (761,784)	1100 (1100,1130)	1098 (1080,1160)	1367 (1366,1426)	1032 (1028,1055)

C. Kube-burner

Kube-burner is an open-source benchmarking tool used for scalability and performance assessment of K8s clusters through automated and realistic workload scenarios. In these lines, we have executed 2 customized experiments while changing the following experimental variables i.e., the number of iterations, the number of concurrent pod deployments/apps, as well as the requested queries and burst per second. All experiments are executed in separate namespaces with a varying number of pod deployments (from 10 to 50), testing the K8s distributions' performance, hardware footprint, pod latency (i.e., the time taken for all application pods to communicate), and scalability under these conditions.

1) *Curl-Webserver Scenario*: This configuration specifies a performance benchmarking scenario that deploys 3 K8s workloads—a webserver deployment, a service, and a curl deployment—while measuring pod latency. In particular, the webserver hosts a simple HTTP application, the webserver service provides an endpoint for that application, and the curl deployment tests connectivity and latency by sending HTTP requests to the webserver.

2) *PostgreSQL-Backend Scenario*: This configuration examines a more demanding client/server application scenario, evaluating how efficiently K8s handles heavier, database-dependent workloads. Specifically, it creates 3 primary deployments—a running PostgreSQL, a service, and a "perfapp" container. By incorporating a stateful database, this workload offers a more realistic assessment of the cluster's capabilities and pod stressing management under high-load conditions.

V. RESULTS

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the considered K8s distributions and plugins, following the aforementioned methodology setup, while also visualizing the scenarios' resource footprint by fetching metrics from Prometheus.

A. Idle State Resource Footprint

Table II presents the median values, along with minimum and maximum ranges, of CPU and RAM utilization during the idle state across all evaluated K8s distributions and plugins for both the master node and one worker node. In particular, the results follow the expected behavior with lightweight distributions i.e., K3s, MK8s and K0s consuming overall lower resources compared to vanilla K8s.

The higher CPU consumption of MK8s on master nodes is justified as all its components are prebuilt and distributed as Snap packages which introduces additional resource overhead. Conversely, this contributes to lower CPU and RAM consumption on MK8s worker nodes, as fewer system components are actively managed. On the contrary, K3s worker nodes use higher CPU and RAM than master nodes due to the lack of a dedicated control plane separation i.e., unlike traditional K8s distributions, where control plane operations are handled exclusively by master nodes, K3s distributes some workloads across worker nodes, leading to increased resource utilization.

In terms of CNI plugins, we observe that Flannel results in lower CPU and RAM usage for all distributions compared to Calico. An exception is observed for the MK8s-Flannel worker, in which the idle CPU and RAM are 0.2% and 270MB higher than MK8s-Calico, respectively. Here, we should note that MK8s uses Calico as the default CNI.

B. Pod Readiness Time

Fig. 2 illustrates the average time required for a batch of "pause" pods to be ready, ranging from a single pod to 100 pods. The pod readiness times vary significantly, affected by both the selection of K8s distribution and the network plugin. The readiness times range from as low as 1 second for a single pod to as high as 43 seconds for 100 pods, for MK8s Calico.

Regarding CNI plugins, Flannel exhibits shorter pod readiness times than Calico, particularly as the number of pods increases. At 100 pods, the K8s and K3s implementations of Flannel require approximately 5 and 12 seconds less time, respectively, to reach readiness compared to their Calico counterparts. This behavior can be justified, as Flannel's simplified architecture minimizes the computational overhead which leads to faster pod setup. However, an exception is observed with MK8s-Flannel, which demonstrates degraded performance under high pod counts.

In terms of K8s distributions, K0s and K3s consistently outperform all other implementations across different pod deployments. An exception is observed for K3s-Calico, which requires 3 additional seconds to reach pod readiness compared to vanilla K8s at 100 pods. In addition, up to 40 pods, the pod readiness times of all lightweight distributions remain lower than those of vanilla K8s (e.g., at 20 pods, K8s-Calico and K8s-Flannel require at least 1.5 seconds more time than their respective lightweight counterparts). However, beyond this threshold, some lightweight distributions exhibit significantly worse performance compared to vanilla K8s. In particular, MK8s-Flannel and K3s-Calico require more than 10 seconds when deploying 100 pods, highlighting potential scalability limitations in high-load scenarios.

This finding highlights a critical trade-off between the inherent reduced system requirements of lightweight K8s distributions (refer to the idle state metrics in Table II) and their performance under higher loads. Therefore, some lightweight distributions may not be optimized to handle high-stressing workloads, as their design likely prioritizes reduced resource consumption over high scalability.

Fig. 2: Average pod readiness times for deployed pods ranging from 1 to 100.

C. Kube-burner

Figs. 3a,b illustrate the average pod latency for the two Kube-burner scenarios, as described in Section IV-C, where an increasing number of simultaneously deployed pod deployments/apps (from 10 to 50) facilitate communication in a curl-webserver, and a PostgreSQL-backend scenario. Due to space limitations, we present only the results of query and burst sizes set to 10, i.e., indicated as $qb10-app<number_of_pod_apps>$ in the x-axis. However, different sizes result in similar patterns.

In Fig. 3a, it becomes evident that the selection of a lightweight K8s distribution significantly reduces pod latency as the number of deployments increases in the curl-webserver scenario. For instance, a reduction of 1.5 seconds is observed between K8s-Calico (4.2 seconds) and K3s-Calico (2.7 seconds), as well as between K8s-Flannel (5.5 seconds) and MK8s-Flannel (4 seconds), while the largest gap occurs at almost 3 seconds between K8s-Flannel and K3s-Calico at 50 pod deployments. Among all lightweight distributions, K3s- and MK8s-Calico exhibit the lowest pod latency, along with MK8s-Flannel. In this context, we also observe a lower deviation of the results for K3s-Calico and K0s-Calico as the number of pod deployments increases, indicating greater reliability. Furthermore, significant variations are observed when selecting a different networking configuration. Surprisingly, Calico consistently outperforms Flannel across all distributions as the number of pod deployments increases, maintaining a pod latency reduction of up to 1.5 seconds.

In terms of resource footprint, Figs. 4a,b present the CPU and RAM consumption observed at the worker node. As shown in Fig. 4a, lightweight K8s distributions consistently maintain lower CPU utilization than vanilla K8s, except the Calico-based configurations at 50 deployments, where K3s and MK8s exceed the CPU consumption of vanilla K8s.

The largest observed gap across all tested distributions and plugins (at 5.6%) occurs between K0s-Calico and K8s-Calico; focusing on plugins alone, a 5% CPU difference is observed between K8s-Calico and K8s-Flannel at 50 deployments. Fig.

(a) Curl-Webserver Scenario

(b) PostgreSQL-Backend Scenario

Fig. 3: Average pod latency of Kube-burner scenarios (a) and (b) with varying number of pod deployments.

(a) CPU Usage of worker node

(b) RAM Usage of worker node

(c) CPU Usage of worker node

(d) RAM Usage of worker node

Fig. 4: Average resource consumption of Curl-Webserver (a,b) and PostgreSQL-Backend (c,d) Kube-burner scenarios with varying number of pod deployments.

4b shows that K3s consistently consumes more RAM (by up to 150 MB) than the other distributions for both Calico and Flannel, mirroring its idle behavior (see Table II). In contrast, MK8s delivers the strongest performance in most scenarios, particularly with Flannel, which reduces RAM usage by up to 500 MB compared to K3s-Flannel. Overall, for CPU and RAM metrics in this scenario, MK8s-Flannel and K0s-Calico demonstrate the best performance.

Fig. 3b evaluates pod latency in a more time and resource-intensive scenario, where establishing communication among

multiple PostgreSQL servers and backends ranges from 19 seconds (K0s-Calico, 10 deployments) up to 33.5 seconds (K8s-Calico, 50 deployments).

Regarding the resource usage, Fig. 4c confirms the CPU intensity of this scenario, peaking at 45%, compared to 33%, in Figure 4a. Once again, noticeable differences emerge among the distributions and plugins. For example, K3s consumes up to 7.5% more CPU in certain deployment cases, while at 50 deployments, the CPU gap between K8s-Calico and MK8s-Flannel reaches 20%. Similarly, Fig. 4d reveals large

disparities in RAM usage across different K8s distributions, with the maximum variation observed between K8s-Flannel and MK8s-Flannel (750MB) at 50 deployments. At the same time, changing the networking fabric can also significantly affect the memory consumption e.g., up to 500MB between K8s-Calico and K8s-Flannel.

VI. DISCUSSION

The summarized key outcomes of the experimentation analysis are as follows:

- The operational requirements of a given application or workload, may favor the selection of a particular solution (e.g., distribution or network). However, it is also crucial to evaluate how these solutions perform under varying stress conditions. Our results show that utilizing different K8s distributions and CNI plugins (e.g., K8s-Flannel or MK8s-Flannel) involves significant trade-offs in both performance and resource usage.
- The implementation differences of K8s distributions and CNI plugins can produce varying results even if only the distribution changes while the plugin remains the same, or conversely, if the plugin is changed but the distribution remains constant.
- Lightweight K8s distributions do not guarantee enhanced performance or lower resource consumption. For example, the results on pod readiness times indicate that MK8s and K3s perform worse than vanilla K8s under heavy workloads, whereas K0s demonstrates the best overall performance. Although lightweight distributions consume fewer resources in their idle state, their runtime resource usage (e.g., CPU and RAM) may surpass that of more resource-intensive alternatives, particularly under high-load conditions. Therefore, the trade-off between the lower system requirements of lightweight distributions and their performance should be considered in scenarios that require high availability and resilience under stress conditions, as their design often prioritizes minimal resource consumption.
- CNI plugins considered as lightweight, such as Flannel, may exhibit degraded performance under heavy-stressing conditions. For instance, in the Kube-burner scenarios, Flannel performs similarly or even worse than theoretically "heavier" alternatives such as Calico. However, in certain metrics such as pod readiness times, Flannel demonstrates superior performance, leveraging its lightweight design to enable faster pod startup. The resource usage for the evaluated plugins also varies significantly depending on the workload. While lightweight plugins generally demand the fewest resources in idle states, under intense load (e.g., in the Kube-burner scenarios), their RAM and CPU consumption can surpass that of vanilla K8s counterparts (see Fig. 4b,c).

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, we conducted a comprehensive evaluation of widely used K8s distributions, some specifically designed for

edge environments, along with two CNI plugins, under a range of stress-testing and realistic scenarios. Our study revealed the selection of the appropriate K8s distribution and networking solution should take into account not only the inherent platform requirements and specifications, but also the scenario-specific needs and constraints. For instance, lightweight K8s distributions and plugins (e.g., MK8s and Flannel) may exhibit lower performance and higher resource consumption compared to resource-intensive counterparts (e.g., vanilla K8s and Calico), especially in high-load scenarios. In future work, we plan to extend this evaluation by: (i) incorporating a broader set of stress-testing tools, such as chaos engineering; (ii) expanding the set of measured metrics including power consumption or cost, in line with application-specific needs and scalability factors; and (iii) evaluating additional workloads with diverse resource and performance demands e.g., for edge-constrained scenarios and devices such as Raspberry Pi, or varied cluster topologies.

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REFERENCES

- [1] H. Koziolok and N. Eskandani, "Lightweight Kubernetes Distributions: A Performance Comparison of MicroK8s, K3s, K0s, and Microshift," in *Proc. ACM/SPEC ICPE*, Coimbra, Portugal, 2023, p. 17–29.
- [2] S. Qi, S. G. Kulkarni, and K. K. Ramakrishnan, "Assessing container network interface plugins: Functionality, performance, and scalability," *IEEE Trans. Netw. Service Manag.*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 656–671, 2021.
- [3] G. Koukis, S. Skaperas, I. A. Kapetanidou, L. Mamatas, and V. Tsaous-sidis, "Evaluating cni plugins features & tradeoffs for edge cloud applications," in *IEEE Symp. Comput. Commun. (ISCC)*, 2024, pp. 1–6.
- [4] V. Kjorveziroski and S. Filiposka, "Kubernetes distributions for the edge: serverless performance evaluation," *J. Supercomputing*, vol. 78 13728–13755, pp. 1–28, 2022.
- [5] G. Koukis, S. Skaperas, I. A. Kapetanidou, L. Mamatas, and V. Tsaous-sidis, "Performance evaluation of kubernetes networking approaches across constraint edge environments," in *IEEE Symp. Comput. Commun. (ISCC)*, 2024, pp. 1–6.
- [6] S. Böhm and G. Wirtz, "Profiling lightweight container platforms: Microk8s and K3s in Comparison to Kubernetes," in *Proc. ZEUS*, Bamberg, Germany, 2021, vol. 2389, pp. 65–73.
- [7] J. Noor *et al.*, "Kubernetes application performance benchmarking on heterogeneous cpu architecture: An experimental review," *High-Confidence Computing*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. 100276, 2025.
- [8] A. Pereira Ferreira and R. Sinnott, "A performance evaluation of containers running on managed kubernetes services," in *IEEE Int. Conf. on Cloud Comput. Technol. Sci. (CloudCom)*, 2019, pp. 199–208.
- [9] Q. Lei *et al.*, "Performance and scalability testing strategy based on kubemark," in *IEEE Int. Conf. on Cloud Comput. and Big Data Anal. (ICCCBDA)*, 2019, pp. 511–516.
- [10] G. Koukis, S. Skaperas, A. Kapetanidou, L. Mamatas, and V. Tsaous-sidis, "An open-source experimentation framework for the edge cloud continuum," in *Proc IEEE INFOCOM Workshops CNERT*, 2024.
- [11] I. M. Ramadan, C. Centofanti, A. Marotta, and F. Graziosi, "Evaluating kubernetes distributions: Insights from stress testing scenarios," in *17th IEEE Int. Conf. Commun. Syst. Netw. (COMSNETS)*, 2025, pp. 13–18.
- [12] S. Telenyk *et al.*, "A Comparison of Kubernetes and Kubernetes-Compatible Platforms," in *Proc. IEEE IDAACS*, Cracow, Poland, 2021, pp. 313–317.
- [13] Kube-Burner, "Kube-burner: Kubernetes Performance and Scalability Testing," <https://kubernetes.github.io/kube-burner/>, Online; Accessed: 05 March 2025.
- [14] XCP-ng, "XCP-ng: The extended XenServer Hypervisor," <https://xcp-ng.org/>, Online; Accessed: 05 March 2025.